

21SCP01 DCC2GO

D1: Freely available, Digital Calibration Certificates (DCC) training compendium of basic knowledge for stakeholders with no prior knowledge of DCCs, with particular focus on the SEND community and supporting a harmonised level of basic DCC knowledge within the European metrology community

Lead partner: PTB

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